

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Jeso

FIRST NAME: Mohamed

PROGRAM CODE: MBIF

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Deleted:

Deleted:

Deleted: Kabiru

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

THE IMPORTNT OF ACADEMIC WRITING**1) INTRODUCTION**

Deleted: ¶

Academic writing is essential when it comes to academic studies, it can be easy to understand the structure of using one universally accepted formula or style. Before I enrolled EUCLID, I had no idea about what is called Zotero application, and the way it is used for references, also I was not familiar with Turabian style, although during my previous academic study I used different styles and sometimes not considering specific and unique type of formulations. The UCLID coursepack gives me a lot of important information relating how to write an academic writing using one standard response paper writing, quite a number of students across different fields are having problem how to write proper academic writing because they were not taught about academic writing and the different rules of style.

Deleted: ¶

Deleted: s

2) GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

Deleted: ¶

The main thing to ponder is before one tries to write an academic paper, first he must have enough information relating to the topic and must also read more relevant to what is intended to write, than it will be easier for the writer to gather more sources that can help to accomplish excellent academic writing. The most essential elements I came across when writing this paper is the information I got from the coursepack, it helped me with the best structural guidelines such as knowing how to write an essay; and starting to draft what should I plan in writing after researching the topic; An academic essay should contain more information with evidence sources (EULID 2015, 2).

Deleted: ¶

It is essential to have read the area of the research, then drafting the idea that may use as tools for proper writing, after that one needs to formulize the introduction, the body of the writing considering the paragraphs rules; I used indent to each paragraph to follow the

Deleted: ¶

instruction requirements. The other requirement is the indent of quotations which contains many sentences as the same margins indented the first line of the paragraph (EULID 2015, 70).

Another thing which concerns the proper writing is the related conclusions at the end of writing. The conclusion is where the reader gets the main concept of text, the understanding of the whole content of writing depends on how the conclusion is relevant to the subject matter. I studied from the coursepack explanations on the structure of essay writing while classifying the three components- introduction, body of the text, and conclusions. The efficient structure of any writing is based on the way the writer attracts the reader, what I clearly understood from the material is avoiding procrastination and starting to think and gather more ideas earlier though planning (EULID 2015, 4).

Deleted: ¶

1) REFERENCING

Deleted: ¶

After going through the coursepack, I discovered many referencing elements that boosted my writing skills into academic standards, going through it I learned to use an in-text citation, how to use different styles of APA and Turabian from Microsoft Word which are built-in options. Although, I have been using the correct procedures of writing a passage, reports, etc., what is new to me is using the rule of styles based on either USA or UK writing style. What I learned from this course is how to cite quotations and the way of point about paraphrases.

Deleted: -

The quotations are the original words of the author. For any writing, when using quotations, first and foremost double quotation marks is necessary to confine or to keep the original words of author in order to be separated from main text of the writer, therefore, it is not necessary to use more or lengthy quotations as it reduces the main objective of the writing. It is also advisable for using quotations that have a strong meaning that makes the writing more persuasive (EULID 2019, 19).

The paraphrases are different from quotations in written text, through the coursepack, it explains clearly the rules of using paraphrases and how to use them as necessary, what I learned is using more paraphrases of my words that is not resembling the author's writing. Paraphrases can be an alternative for a few cases to make it less using more quotations in any writing (EULID 2019, 24).

2) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE (TURABIAN)

Deleted: ¶

Chicago style is for students and researchers. It is writing style making more standard just like other universally accepted norms of using the same kind of compatibilities such as weight measurements, mechanical tools, and other equipment. For this style the coursepack material explains clearly and the video clip in LMS helps me to understand and use in any of my writings in the future. This coursepack is part of my knowledge and understanding of how to write an academic paper.

Deleted: ¶

Chicago style for page formats has many rules such as margins, fonts, indents, spacing formulas when selected as a rule of the particular writing which all in necessary for any paper to apply as standard. The coursepack also explained deeply is the order of citations

Deleted: ¶

of endnotes and footnotes. One of the rules indicates that avoiding double-spacing the citation or not using punctuation at the end of a sentence (EUCLID 2015, 67).

The most important thing which Turabian style appropriately uses for students from MS Word creating the citation formula in easy steps without any interruption for the time of writing. The main objective of using is to protect the rights of originator's ideas, any writing should be free from any plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 12). In reference list style has to approaches in any writing using Chicago style, that is first mentioning the author's name, date, and relevant pager number (Turabian 2013, 131).

Any writer should strict to his/her unique area of knowledge and make the thing more personal instead of using other's ideas without mentioning the ownership of its originator. That way references the essay is so important for any writer. When you mention through citation someone else's work, give the author the identity he or she has earned (Turabian 2013, 128).

When studying the course material, I learned a lot of processes relating to using CMS for courses and LMS for learning materials including video clips which give me a clear picture, although many things are new to me, I tried to understand after spending more time. This case I hope will assist me to go smoothly to accomplish the remaining course.

Deleted:

3) CONCLUSION

Chicago style is designed for students and researchers writing research papers, writing the framework for making more standards like other universally accepted norms for use of presenting such as weight, measurement, mechanical devices standard, and other equipment. This method where the coursepack is explicitly explained as well as the LMS video view helps me understand. This handbook is part of my knowledge and understanding of how to write academic papers. Chicago's structure of pages has many rules such as margins, fonts, indents, spacing formulas.

Deleted: s

Quotations are the original words of the author, the writer cannot use the same sentence from other similar authors, nor are words originated from their intelligence. Every note, when using quotation marks the first square is necessary to keep the words of the original author from distinguishing the main text of the writer. The paraphrases are different from the quotations in the text, and as a writing purpose, it defines the rules of using the writer's word explaining the real words of the originated author and also giving the author his credit using Turabian style of citations.

Deleted: ¶

That academic writing is essential when it comes to academic studies, and it can be formally simple to use a single widely accepted formula or method. Before writing this response paper, I had no idea what Zotero applications are called and how they are used in references, and I am not also familiar with the Turabian version, although in my previous academic studies I used different methods and sometimes did not consider a particular type.

Deleted: ¶

EUCLID provides an important information about how to write academic writing using one common style.

Deleted: ¶

Deleted: ¶

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.